

CODE-FORMATTED THEORETICAL DESIGN EQUATIONS FOR SHEAR STRENGTHENING OF RC BEAMS USING NEAR-SURFACE MOUNTED FRP REINFORCEMENT

Amir Mofidi, Brock University, Canada, amir.mofidi@brocku.ca
Lijuan (Dawn) Cheng, University of California, Davis, USA, dawcheng@ucdavis.edu
Omar Chaallal, École de Technologie Supérieure, Canada, omar.chaallal@etsmtl.ca
Mona Rajabifard, Brock University, Canada, mrajabifard@brocku.ca
Yixin Shao, McGill University, Canada, yixin.shao@mcgill.ca

ABSTRACT

This paper presents accurate, reliable and practical theoretical design equations for reinforced-concrete (RC) beams strengthened in shear with Near-Surface Mounted (NSM) FRP reinforcement. Unlike other existing design equations, the proposed design equations can be used for RC beams strengthened with both NSM FRP bars and laminate, and are capable of predicting the failure mode of the NSM-strengthened beams. A state-of-the-art fracture mechanics-based NSM bond model has been incorporated to develop the proposed evolutionary design equations. The accuracy of the proposed design equations was validated using relevant experimental studies in the literature. The proposed design equations were able to achieve superior accuracy when the predicted results were compared with those of the existing models in the literature using different statistical measures.

KEYWORDS

Concrete beams; near-surface mounted; FRP shear rehabilitation; shear resistance; bond model; fracture mechanics; and design model.

INTRODUCTION

Recently, valuable efforts have been directed toward the understanding and application of fibre-reinforced polymer (FRP) composites for strengthening concrete structures. Experimental and analytical studies have been conducted on the strengthening of reinforced concrete (RC) members using various methods based on FRP reinforcement (e.g., Chaallal *et al.* 1998, De Lorenzis and Nanni 2001, and Galal and Mofidi 2010). Among these research efforts, the rehabilitation of concrete beams in shear using the Near-Surface Mounted (NSM) FRP technique has gained noticeable attention. The idea originated in the 1940s when Asplund (1949) grouted NSM steel rods to strengthen a bridge slab in flexure. Fifty years later, Nanni *et al.* (1999) rehabilitated a highway bridge in flexure using NSM FRP rods.

Shear strengthening using the NSM FRP method was investigated for the first time by De Lorenzis and Nanni (2001) through experimental testing of six RC beams, focusing on variables such as the spacing of the rods, the FRP bar inclination angle, the end-anchorage of the FRP bars, and the presence of internal steel shear reinforcement. In their study, a model was proposed to predict the contribution of NSM FRP strengthening to the shear resistance of RC beams. Subsequently, several experimental studies on shear strengthening of RC beams using NSM FRP have contributed to the topic (e.g., Parretti and Nanni 2004, Rizzo and De Lorenzis 2007, Kotynia 2007, Chaallal *et al.* 2011, and Mofidi *et al.* 2016). Barros and Dias (2006) conducted an investigation on eight rectangular RC beams strengthened with NSM FRP laminates. The experimental parameters of their studies included the spacing and the inclination angle of the laminates, the ratio of longitudinal steel reinforcement, and the ratio of internal steel shear reinforcement. Rizzo and De Lorenzis (2007) investigated the behaviour of seven rectangular RC beams retrofitted in shear using FRP bars and laminates. The effectiveness of FRP bars versus FRP laminates and the effects of adhesive type, FRP reinforcement inclination angle, and the spacing between the FRP reinforcement components were their major test

parameters. Kotynia (2007) conducted eight tests on shear-strengthened RC beams with NSM FRP laminates. The test parameters were the spacing and inclination of the FRP laminates. A series of tests were also conducted by Dias and Barros (2008, 2010, 2011, 2012, and 2013) using NSM FRP laminates. The test variables in their studies included various influential parameters such as concrete compressive strength, pre-cracking of the specimens, internal steel shear reinforcement, the spacing of the FRP reinforcement, and the FRP reinforcement angle. Anwarul Islam (2009) tested three shear-strengthened rectangular RC specimens using NSM FRP bars up to failure. The test parameters included the effect of internal steel shear reinforcement and the spacing of NSM FRP bars. Wiwatrojanagul *et al.* (2012) studied the effect of FRP bar materials (Aramid FRP versus Carbon FRP), the inclination and the spacing of FRP bars on six shear-strengthened RC beams with NSM FRP rods. They concluded that decreasing the spacing between FRP bars did not necessarily lead to increases in the shear capacity of the strengthened specimens, since this might lead to a concrete cover splitting type of failure. Rahal and Rumaih (2011) investigated the effect of FRP bar inclination, FRP bar end-anchorage, and NSM FRP bars type (FRP versus steel bars) on three 3250 mm-long RC beams. Extending the NSM bars into one specimen's concrete flange increased the shear resistance and prevented the concrete cover from splitting in the specimen. Cisneros *et al.* (2012) studied the effect of the inclination, the cross-sectional shape (bars versus laminates) and the spacing of the NSM FRP composites on sixteen test specimens. Raj and Surumi (2012) tested ten shear-strengthened rectangular RC specimens using NSM FRP bars and laminates. The test parameters were the FRP bars/laminates inclinations and the spacing between the FRP bars/laminates.

The results of these studies have led to a few analytical models and design equations. These models, however, are difficult to implement in code format for prediction and design purposes. This could be due to the inherent shortcomings and limitations in these models, where certain key influencing parameters are not properly captured and incorporated into the model affecting its accuracy (Mofidi *et al.* 2018). One of the most important categories, which is the focal point of this article, is related to the formulation of the effective strain in FRP. In general, the effective FRP strain should be calculated in association with a logical and accurate bond model between NSM FRP and the concrete surface. Several such bond models have been developed by researchers [e.g., Seracino *et al.* (2007) and Zhang *et al.* (2011)], however, these bond models have not been incorporated into practical equations for the current design models, which still use fixed values or empirical equations for effective FRP strain. In this regard, Aghamohammadi *et al.* (2021) investigated the reliability of the models proposed by Seracino *et al.* (2007) and Zhang *et al.* (2011) through a reliability analysis based on the first-order second-moment method for both laminates and bars accounting for uncertainties due to geometrical and mechanical properties of the NSM FRP-to-concrete joints. The study by Aghamohammadi *et al.* (2021) revealed that Seracino *et al.* (2007) bond model is more reliable to predict the results related to NSM FRP bars rather than those of NSM FRP laminates. However, when considering all failure modes, the reliability of Zhang *et al.* (2011) model is higher to predict the NSM FRP laminates bond strength than that of NSM FRP bars (Aghamohammadi *et al.* 2021).

This research gap has been the main impetus to carry out the present study which aims at evaluating the existing design procedures in the literature regarding the shear contribution of NSM FRP in shear-strengthened RC beams. In addition, theoretical design models with practical equations are proposed in this study for estimating the shear resistance of NSM-strengthened RC beams. These models are capable of predicting different possible failure modes for RC beams strengthened with NSM FRP bars and laminates. The accuracy of the proposed design equations is validated with the experimental data in the literature.

SYNTHESIS OF CURRENT RESEARCH AND PRACTICE

Literature Data on Key Parameters

Over the past decade, several studies (e.g., De Lorenzis and Nanni 2001, Rizzo and De Lorenzis 2007, Kotynia 2007, and Mofidi *et al.* 2016) have been carried out to experimentally evaluate the parameters affecting the contribution of NSM FRP to the shear resistance of strengthened RC beams. These studies have identified several major parameters that affect the shear contribution of NSM FRP

to shear resistance. Some of these parameters have been successfully included in the analytical models (e.g., cross-sectional area and FRP mechanical characteristics, NSM FRP inclination, etc.). However, as previously discussed, several other key parameters have not yet been captured by the existing design models.

Failure modes

The specimens in the literature displayed a number of different failure modes, such as FRP debonding, transverse and longitudinal concrete cover splitting, and FRP fracture (Mofidi *et al.* 2016). The existing analytical models and equations do not provide separate equations for different types of failure modes. A thorough examination of these failure modes is much needed to enhance the understanding of the resistance mechanisms of NSM shear-strengthened RC beams.

Bond model

Debonding of FRP is the most likely governing failure mode for RC beams shear-strengthened with NSM FRP. The most rational and commonly accepted method to predict debonding of NSM FRP used for shear strengthening of RC beams is by using a reliable bond model. Several researchers have proposed various bond models based on experimental studies on NSM FRP-to-concrete joint tests. De Lorenzis (2004) conducted several valuable tests considering different FRP materials, shapes and groove configurations on NSM FRP bars-to-concrete joints. She proposed different local bond stress-slip relationships for NSM FRP-to-concrete joints for different test variables. It was concluded that a general bond-slip model that considers geometry and material property functions should be developed (De Lorenzis and Teng 2007). Seracino *et al.* (2007) proposed a generic fracture mechanics-based model to predict the debonding resistance of adhesively bonded plate-to-concrete joints using an idealized linear-softening local interface bond-slip relationship, which is also applicable to NSM FRP/concrete joints. In addition, Zhang *et al.* (2011) also proposed a state-of-the-art fracture mechanics-based bond model for NSM FRP/concrete joints. However, most of the existing analytical models for shear strengthening of RC beams with NSM FRP do not use any bond model, which can lead to possible inaccuracies in the predicted results of such design models (Mofidi *et al.* 2016).

Effective strain

Assuming that the NSM FRP reinforcement carries only normal stresses in the principal FRP material direction, NSM FRP may be treated by a similar analogy to the transverse steel stirrups. In this case, all FRP bars or laminates intersected by the selected shear crack are assumed to contribute the same FRP effective strain. The effective strain, ε_{fe} , in the principal material direction is, in general, less than the tensile strain at failure, ε_{fu} .

In recent years, researchers have proposed various equations to calculate ε_{fe} (e.g., Kotynia 2007, Dias and Barros 2013). However, none of these existing equations incorporates a reliable NSM FRP bond model. Mofidi *et al.* (2016), taking advantage of the state-of-the-art bond model by Seracino *et al.* (2007), were able to calculate the effective strain in the FRP using the equilibrium conditions in the NSM FRP bars or laminates. Before debonding, the force in the FRP is equal to the maximum bonding force between the FRP and the concrete surface. The force that can be developed in the NSM FRP on one side of the beam can be calculated using the bonding model. The effective strain corresponding to FRP debonding was calculated afterwards.

Effective bond length

Empirically, for NSM FRP bars or laminates bonded with an FRP anchorage length greater than the effective bond length, the ultimate tensile force is limited to the force corresponding to the effective anchorage length. Note that the FRP anchorage length is a parameter dependent on the RC beam's size. This implies that the bond strength does not necessarily increase steadily and constantly with the bond length. This also explains the rationale behind the important concept of effective bond length, defined as the length beyond which the bond strength remains constant.

For NSM FRP bars and laminates, Seracino *et al.* (2007) proposed equations for a bi-linear fracture mechanics model to calculate the effective bond length as follows:

$$L_{ef} = \frac{\pi}{2\lambda} \tag{Eq. 1}$$

$$\lambda^2 = \frac{\tau_{max} L_{per}}{\delta_{max} E_f A_f} \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

where τ_{max} and δ_{max} are, respectively, the maximum shear stress and the maximum slip, assuming a bilinear bond-slip relationship at the concrete/epoxy interface. The maximum shear stress and maximum slip are calculated on the basis of an empirical equation extracted from a statistical analysis (Seracino *et al.* 2007). That is,

$$\tau_{max} = (0.802 + 0.078\varphi_f) f_c'^{0.6} \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

$$\delta_{max} = \frac{0.976\varphi_f^{0.526}}{0.802+0.078\varphi_f} \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

where units of Newton and millimetres are used. Meanwhile, φ_f is the debonding-failure plane aspect ratio that is equal to $(d_f)/(b_f)$. b_f is the length of the failure plane parallel to the concrete surface (at the FRP/concrete interface), which for NSM laminates and rods is taken to be the width of the groove plus 2 mm. In addition, d_f is the length of the failure plane perpendicular to the concrete surface, which for NSM plates is taken to be the depth of the groove plus 1 mm. The other important parameter in Eq. (2) is L_{per} , which is the debonding failure plane in the cross-section and is set equal to $(2d_f + b_f)$ assuming that the effective bond length (L_{ef}) of the FRP bars or laminates is fully available.

Contribution of NSM FRP to Shear Resistance

The nominal shear resistance at the ultimate limit state, V_n , of RC beams strengthened in shear with NSM FRP is generally calculated simply by adding the contribution of FRP reinforcement to the shear resistance, V_f , to that of concrete, V_c , and of transverse steel reinforcement, V_s , as follows (ACI 440.2R-17):

$$V_n = V_c + V_s + V_f \quad \text{Eq. 5}$$

The contributions of concrete and shear steel reinforcement are calculated using the design guidelines for non-strengthened RC structures, assuming that the FRP strengthening does not influence the shear contribution of the concrete or the transverse steel reinforcement (ACI 440.2R-17). This assumption is supported by experimental observations (e.g., Mofidi *et al.* 2016 and Mofidi *et al.* 2018) where steel shear rebars yielded prior to the ultimate failure of the strengthened RC beams.

For the NSM FRP contribution, most existing analytical models use the truss analogy similar to that used to calculate the contribution of steel stirrups (e.g. Kotynia 2007, Anwarul Islam 2009, Jalali *et al.* 2012, Mofidi *et al.* 2016). Thus, the shear contribution of NSM FRP can be obtained by multiplying the ultimate vertical stress in the NSM FRP by the area of the FRP bars or laminates that cross a potential shear crack. All the NSM FRP bars or laminates that intersect the selected shear crack are assumed to contribute the same amount of FRP effective strain. Most of the design guidelines and analytical models to be discussed below basically use a similar design analogy but with different definitions of effective strain. In terms of practicality and ease of use, the selected models are presented in a code format and implemented in standard codes or design guidelines to be used by practicing engineers:

De Lorenzis and Nanni (2001)

In this model, the shear force resisted by the NSM FRP bars is calculated as the sum of the forces resisted by the FRP bars intersected by a shear crack, i.e.,

$$V_f = 2 \sum A_i f_i = 2 \pi d_b \tau_b L_{tot\min} \quad \text{Eq. 6}$$

where A_i is the nominal cross-sectional area of the rods; f_i is the tensile stress in the bar at the crack location; d_b is the bar diameter; $L_{tot\min}$ is the sum of the anchorage lengths of all the bars crossed by the crack in the most unfavourable crack position, i.e., the minimum sum of the anchorage lengths of each bar; and τ_b is the average bond stress between FRP and concrete (a constant value of 6.9 MPa is assumed, i.e., no bond model was adopted). Moreover, in this model, the effective bond length of the

FRP is limited by either the cross-sectional dimensions of the RC beam or the length corresponding to an FRP effective strain of 4000 $\mu\epsilon$. This model was further modified by Parretti and Nanni (2004) to be applicable to NSM FRP laminates in addition to NSM FRP bars. However, the model overall lacks a logical bond model for the reason discussed earlier.

Barros and Dias (2006)

This model follows the model by Parretti and Nanni (2004) but adopted a bond model with a bond stress of 16.1 MPa and an effective strain of 0.0059, which were extracted from the researchers' pull-out tests in order to calculate the shear contribution of NSM FRP laminates in shear strengthened RC beams. The model is expressed by the following equation:

$$V_f = 4 (a_f + b_f) \tau_b L_{tot_{min}} \quad \text{Eq. 7}$$

where a_f and b_f are the dimensions of the laminate's cross-section.

Kotynia (2007)

In this model, the truss analogy was implemented by Kotynia (2007) to calculate the shear contribution of NSM FRP as follows:

$$V_f = \frac{A_f \epsilon_f E_f}{s_f} z (\cot\theta + \cot\alpha) \sin\alpha \quad \text{Eq. 8}$$

where A_f , E_f , α , and s_f are the area of the cross-section, modulus of elasticity, inclination angle and the spacing between NSM FRP, respectively. In addition, z and θ are the inner level arm and the principal shear angle, respectively. The findings of the study suggested that the effective strain in NSM FRP could be assumed as 0.0035 to predict the FRP shear contribution.

Anwarul Islam (2009)

This model used a similar approach to Kotynia's model (2007), except the results suggested that the NSM effective strain should be taken as one-third of the ultimate strain of the FRP rods in calculating the FRP shear contribution. In this model, the principal crack angle is taken as 45°.

Dias and Barros (2013)

A truss analogy was adopted by the researchers in this study. The researchers found that the presence of steel stirrups decreased the effective strain in RC beams strengthened with NSM FRP laminates. This finding is similar to what was already observed for RC beams strengthened with EB FRP [e.g., Pellegrino and Modena (2012), Mofidi and Chaallal (2011), and Mofidi *et al.* (2012)]. However, Mofidi *et al.* (2016) and (2018) revealed that the presence of transverse steel reinforcement does not influence the NSM FRP shear contribution the way it affects the shear contribution of EB FRP fabrics and laminates. In Dias and Barros (2013) study, the effective strain in the FRP is calculated based on curve fitting of the experimental results of their tests, which is a function of the sum of the rigidity of the transverse steel reinforcement and that of the NSM FRP and concrete compressive strength. That is,

$$\epsilon_{fe} = \left[3.76888 \times e^{(-0.1160261\theta_f + 0.0010437\theta_f^2)} \times \left[\frac{(E_f \rho_f + E_s \rho_{sv})}{f_{cm}^{2/3}} \right]^{-0.460679} \times e^{(0.0351199\theta_f - 0.0003431\theta_f^2)} \right] / \gamma_f \quad \text{Eq. 9}$$

where θ_f is FRP inclination angle; E_f and E_s are the moduli of elasticity of FRP and steel in GPa, respectively; f_{cm} is the concrete compressive strength; γ_f is an uncertainty factor with a suggested value of 1.3; ρ_f equals $(2A_f)/(b_w \times s_{f-o})$ with A_f being the cross-sectional area of FRP laminates, b_w the beam's web width, and s_{f-o} the spacing between the FRP laminates in the orthogonal direction ($s_{f-o} = s_{f-h} \times \sin\alpha$ where s_{f-h} is the horizontal spacing of the FRP); and ρ_{sv} is defined as $A_{sv}/(b_w \times s)$, where A_{sv} is the cross-sectional area of steel stirrups and s is the spacing of the stirrups.

Mofidi *et al.* (2016)

Similar to most of the aforementioned analytical models, Mofidi *et al.* (2016) model uses a truss analogy with different definitions of effective strain. The FRP contribution to shear resistance is written in the following form:

$$V_f = \frac{A_f \cdot \varepsilon_{fe} \cdot E_f (\sin \alpha + \cos \alpha) \cdot d_v}{s_f} \quad \text{Eq. 10}$$

In the model proposed by Mofidi *et al.* (2016), the FRP effective strain is the average of the maximum strain carried by the actively involved NSM FRP materials at failure. The corresponding FRP effective strain for all failure modes was evaluated on each side of the major shear crack. The failure mode with the minimum corresponding effective strain to that failure mode was the governing effective strain and was used in the calculation of the FRP contribution to shear resistance. For the debonding failure mode, the effective strain was calculated using the equilibrium equation of the NSM FRP based on the proposed debonding pull-off force (P_{fb}) of the NSM FRP at the concrete/epoxy interface, using Seracino *et al.* (2007) bond model, as follows:

$$P_{fb} = 0.85 \varphi_f^{0.25} \cdot f_c'^{0.33} \sqrt{L_{per} E_f A_f} \quad \text{Eq. 11}$$

The effective FRP strain corresponding to NSM FRP debonding at the concrete/epoxy interface, (ε_{ef-b}), was calculated using:

$$\varepsilon_{ef-b} = \frac{0.4 k_{ef} \cdot \varphi_f^{0.25} \cdot f_c'^{0.33} \sqrt{L_{per}}}{\sqrt{E_f A_f}} \quad \text{Eq. 12}$$

Separate equations have been proposed by Mofidi *et al.* (2016) to predict the concrete cover splitting failure mode. The predicted effective strain in the NSM FRP bars or laminates at ultimate load was taken as the minimum of the strain due to NSM FRP debonding and that of the concrete cover splitting. When the stresses in the failure zone reach the concrete tensile strength, concrete-cover splitting at the RC beam's web takes place. This failure mode can be expected more often in specimens with weak concrete ($f_c' < 30$ MPa) and tightly spaced NSM FRP (Mofidi *et al.* 2018). The concrete splitting capacity (P_{fc}) in Mofidi *et al.* (2016) model was calculated using Seo *et al.* (2012) proposed concrete-cover splitting model for grouped bonded NSM FRP as follows:

$$P_{fc} = 0.57 \beta \sqrt{f_c'} A_{cf} \quad \text{Eq. 13}$$

where f_c' , β , and A_{cf} are the compressive strength of concrete in MPa, an experimental coefficient equal to 0.7, and the surface area of splitting failure of concrete in mm², respectively. The concrete surface area of splitting failure for NSM FRP bars and laminates was calculated as follows, according to Mofidi *et al.* (2016):

$$A_{cf} = L_{total} (3D_f + 0.3L_{mb}) \quad \text{for FRP bars} \quad \text{Eq. 14}$$

$$A_{cf} = L_{total} (2w_f + 0.3L_{mb} + t_f) \quad \text{for FRP laminates} \quad \text{Eq. 15}$$

where L_{mb} , the embedment length, can be taken equal to the minimum of L_{ef} and $d_v/2 \sin \alpha$. Thus, the concrete-cover splitting force is used to calculate the effective strain of NSM FRP corresponding to the concrete-cover splitting failure mode as follows:

$$\varepsilon_{fe-c} = \frac{0.4 \sqrt{f_c'} A_{cf} \cdot s_f}{A_f \cdot E_f \cdot d_v} \quad \text{Eq. 16}$$

PROPOSED THEORETICAL SHEAR DESIGN MODEL

To improve the accuracy and practicality of the existing models in the literature, a new theoretical model with easy-to-use design equations is developed in this study for RC beams strengthened in shear using NSM FRP bars and laminates. The proposed new design equations benefit from the state-

of-the-art NSM bond model proposed by Zhang *et al.* (2011), and can predict the possible failure modes of debonding of FRP and concrete-cover splitting.

Model Description

As mentioned earlier, Aghamohammadi *et al.* (2021) revealed that the NSM FRP bond model by Zhang *et al.* (2011) predicts the NSM FRP laminates bond strength with greater reliability compared to that of NSM FRP bars. They also showed that Seracino *et al.* (2007) bond model, which was used in Mofidi *et al.* (2016) to propose design equations for the shear-strengthened RC beams with NSM FRP, predicts the NSM FRP bars bond strength with higher reliability than that of NSM FRP laminates. Considering the fact that the majority of the specimens in the database were strengthened with NSM FRP laminates, in the newly proposed design equations for RC beams strengthened in shear with NSM FRP, Zhang *et al.* (2011) bond model was used for greater reliability in the predicted results. These modifications to Mofidi *et al.* (2016) design equations only affect the effective strain equations corresponding to debonding failure mode. In the new model, the effective strain is calculated using the equilibrium equation of the NSM FRP based on the proposed pull-off force (P_{fb}) of the NSM FRP at the concrete/epoxy interface, using Zhang *et al.* (2011) bond model, as follows:

$$P_{fb} = \beta_L \sqrt{2G_f E_f A_f C_f} \quad \text{Eq. 17}$$

where

$$G_f = 0.4 \left(\frac{h_g}{w_g} \right)^{0.422} f_c^{0.619} \quad \text{Eq. 18}$$

and the effective length is calculated as follows according to Zhang *et al.* (2011):

$$L_e = \frac{1.66}{\eta} \quad \text{Eq. 19}$$

$$\eta^2 = \frac{\tau_{max}^2 C_f}{2G_f E_f A_f} \quad \text{Eq. 20}$$

In these equations, C_f is the cross-sectional contour of the failure surface, as described in Zhang *et al.* (2011), h_g is the groove height, w_g is the groove width, G_f is the interfacial fracture energy, η is the axial stiffness of bonded joints, and τ_{max} is the maximum shear bond stress calculated as follows:

$$\tau_{max} = 1.15 \left(\frac{h_g}{w_g} \right)^{0.138} f_c^{0.613} \quad \text{Eq. 21}$$

It should be noted that h_g and w_g are dependent on the cross-sectional shape of the NSM FRP laminate or bar. To this end, the effective strain corresponding to debonding failure mode in the new design equations for RC beam strengthened with NSM FRP can be simply written as:

$$\varepsilon_{fe-b} = \sqrt{\frac{G_f C_f}{2E_f A_f}} \quad \text{Eq. 22}$$

It should be noted, in Eq. 22, β_L which is the reduction factor to account for the effect of insufficient bond lengths in Zhang *et al.* (2011) was considered equal to 1. This decision was made due to the fact that the average effective bond length in the specimens in the database, calculated using Eq. 19, was equal to 177.6 mm, which is a bond length that is generally provided in medium to large RC beams. Similarly, k_{ef} the coefficient proposed by Mofidi *et al.* (2016) to account for the effect of insufficient bond length is not considered in the newly-proposed model and is taken equal to 1. This approach will significantly decrease the number of equations in the design model in an attempt to develop practical, accurate, and code-formatted design equations ready to be implemented in the design guidelines and standard codes. This approach, which will be verified in the following sections of this paper, is only valid if the accuracy of the design model is not compromised.

The effective strain corresponding to the concrete cover splitting failure mode is calculated using Eq. 16 as proposed by Mofidi *et al.* (2016). The effective strain used in Eq. 10 to calculate the shear contribution of NSM FRP will be taken equal to:

$$\varepsilon_{fe} = \min(\varepsilon_{fe-b}, \varepsilon_{fe-c})$$

Eq. 23

which will be the decisive equation to reveal the predicted failure mode of the strengthened RC beam as well.

Model Verification

In order to validate the predicted shear resistance of the proposed model, the experimental contributions of NSM FRP to the shear resistance of the retrofitted specimens in the database are compared with the shear resistance predicted by the proposed design equations. The results of specimens that failed with no major contribution of NSM FRP to the shear resistance, those of specimens that failed due to unrelated failure modes to the shear resistance, and those of specimens with special anchorage of NSM FRP are not considered.

The accuracy of the calculated V_f by the proposed model is compared to that of the existing design models in the literature by De Lorenzis and Nanni (2001), Kotynia (2007), Anwarul Islam (2009), Dias and Barros (2009), and Mofidi *et al.* (2016). Figures 1(a) to (f) show the calculated values of NSM FRP shear contribution (V_{fcal}) using the mentioned model versus the experimental values (V_{fexp}).

Figure 1: Predicted versus experimental results by (a) the proposed model; (b) De Lorenzis and Nanni (2001); (c) Kotynia (2007); (d) Anwarul Islam (2009); (e) Dias and Barros (2009); and (f) Mofidi *et al.* (2016) models.

Meanwhile, Table 1 reveals the main statistical measures in this study used to compare the accuracy of the predicting models; namely, ψ = the average V_{exp}/V_{cal} ratio, Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), Normalized Root Mean Square Error (NRMSE), the Coefficient of Determination with respect to the best fit (R^2), the Coefficient of Efficiency (E), i.e., R^2 with respect to 1:1 line, and the Index of Agreement (d), where R^2 , E and d are calculated using Eq. 24, Eq. 25, and Eq. 26 (Legates and McCabe Jr. 1999), respectively:

$$R^2 = \left\{ \frac{\sum(V_{f\ exp} - \bar{V}_{f\ exp})(V_{f\ cal} - \bar{V}_{f\ cal})}{[\sum(V_{f\ exp} - \bar{V}_{f\ exp})^2]^{0.5} [\sum(V_{f\ cal} - \bar{V}_{f\ cal})^2]^{0.5}} \right\}^2 \quad \text{Eq. 24}$$

$$E = 1.0 - \frac{\sum(V_{f\ exp} - V_{f\ cal})^2}{\sum(V_{f\ exp} - \bar{V}_{f\ exp})^2} \quad \text{Eq. 25}$$

$$d = 1.0 - \frac{\sum(V_{f\ exp} - V_{f\ cal})^2}{\sum(|V_{f\ exp} - \bar{V}_{f\ exp}| + |V_{f\ cal} - \bar{V}_{f\ exp}|)^2} \quad \text{Eq. 26}$$

It should be noted that the only models that are applicable for both, NSM FRP laminates and bars, are the proposed model and Mofidi *et al.* (2016) model. The model by De Lorenzis and Nanni (2001) is developed for NSM FRP bars and can not be used for NSM FRP laminates. Therefore, only specimens strengthened with NSM FRP bars are included in the comparisons for De Lorenzis and Nanni (2001) model. The models by Kotynia (2007) and Dias and Barros (2009) were developed based on NSM laminates but can be used for NSM FRP bars. Thus, in the comparisons made for these two models all the specimens strengthened with NSM FRP laminates and bars are considered. The model by Anwarul Islam (2009) was developed based on NSM bars but can be used for NSM FRP laminates. Hence, all the tested specimens strengthened with NSM FRP laminates and bars are considered in the comparisons related to this model.

When it comes to producing conservative results, De Lorenzis and Nanni (2001) produced the most conservative results with $\psi=1.46$ followed by Kotynia (2007) model with ψ equal to 1.27. The proposed model produced a conservative and economical value for ψ , equal to 1.13. The MAE is the least for the proposed model (MAE = 16.85 kN) followed by the models by Dias and Barros (2009) and Mofidi *et al.* (2016) with MAEs equal to 20.42 kN and 21.38 kN, correspondingly. The proposed model produced the lowest RMSE, equal to 20.20 kN followed by the models by De Lorenzis and Nanni (2001), and Mofidi *et al.* (2016) with RMSEs equal to 27.15 kN for both cases.

When comparing the NRMSE, the most accurate models are the proposed model (NRMSE = 0.35) followed by the models by Mofidi *et al.* (2016) and Dias and Barros (2009) with NRMSEs equal to 0.47 and 0.48, respectively (Table 1).

Table 1: Statistical indicators to compare the accuracy of the design models

Model/Parameter	ψ	MAE (kN)	RMSE (kN)	NRMSE	R^2	E	d
Proposed model	1.13	16.85	20.20	0.35	0.503	0.431	0.836
De Lorenzis and Nanni (2001)	1.46	22.62	27.15	0.51	0.320	-0.059	0.737
Kotynia (2007)	1.27	38.15	51.77	0.90	0.035	-0.096	0.447
Anwarul Islam (2009)	0.85	65.23	94.67	1.65	0.001	-11.502	0.222
Dias and Barros (2009)	1.01 (0.85)*	20.42 (18.00)	27.73 (23.68)	0.48 (0.42)	0.114 (0.436)	-0.072 (0.286)	0.592 (0.779)
Mofidi <i>et al.</i> (2016)	1.10	21.38	27.15	0.47	0.494	-0.037	0.801

* The values between parentheses for Dias and Barros (2009) model are produced considering only the specimens strengthened with NSM FRP laminates.

Evaluating the scatter of the predicted versus experimental results using three statistical measures including R^2 , E , and d reveals that the most accurate model is the proposed model with $R^2 = 0.503$, $E = 0.431$, and $d = 0.836$. The proposed model is followed by Mofidi *et al.* (2016) model with $R^2 = 0.494$, $E = -0.037$, and $d = 0.801$ and the model proposed by De Lorenzis and Nanni (2001) with $R^2 = 0.320$, $E = -0.059$, and $d = 0.737$. The rather undesirable R^2 , E , and d values in Table 1 for Kotynia (2007), Anwarul Islam (2009), and Dias and Barros (2009) models suggest that the models may not be suitable to be used for both NSM FRP bars and laminates, which presumably was not the objective of the mentioned researchers in the first place. However, it can be seen in Table 1 that the model by Dias and Barros (2009), for example, produces considerably accurate results when only the NSM FRP laminate specimens are considered.

Nevertheless, Table 1 clearly shows that the proposed model outperforms the existing models proposed by other researchers in all considered statistical measures, using design equations that are easy-to-use, practical, and straightforward.

CONCLUSIONS

A new theoretical design model is proposed in this study for calculating the shear contribution of FRP bars and laminates in RC beams strengthened in shear using the NSM FRP method. Unlike, most existing analytical models, the new design model uses a state-of-the-art bond model, can be used for both FRP laminates and FRP bars, and can predict the failure mode of the strengthened RC beams. Based on the easy-to-use approach picked up in this paper, the design equations can be considered code-formatted and practical. The design equations are an improved version of the design equations from the same authors published in Mofidi *et al.* (2016) in terms of accuracy and practicality. They clearly featured an enhanced performance compared to the existing design models in the literature based on the following indicators:

- the proposed model shows an excellent correlation with the experimental results in the literature and was significantly superior compared to the other existing design models ($R^2 = 0.503$, $E = 0.431$, and $d = 0.836$);

- with respect to the produced errors, the proposed model was able to produce more precise values with the least errors compared to the rest of the models (MAE = 16.85 kN, RMSE = 20.20 kN, and NRMSE = 0.35);
- the easy-to-use approach of the proposed design model led to simple steps in the calculation of V_f without compromising the proposed model's accuracy.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.